

An Explicit Public Certificate for G63 with Cut Value 27,052

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Abstract

We report an explicit Max-Cut assignment with cut value 27,052 for the G63 instance in the G-set benchmark. The highest-scoring previously published explicit public certificate we identified has value 27,047, reported by Khan and Shukla [2]. We provide the present assignment as a plain hexadecimal string and verify the reported value by recomputing the cut from the standard G63 edge list. We do not claim optimality of 27,052; the contribution of this note is to publish an explicit public certificate attaining this value and to document a direct recomputation procedure.

1 Introduction

The G-set collection is a standard benchmark for the Max-Cut problem [1]. We focus on G63, which has 7,000 vertices and 41,459 edges. In this note, we use the term *explicit public certificate* to mean a public vertex assignment from which the cut value can be recomputed directly.

Khan and Shukla [2] reported an explicit public certificate with cut value 27,047 for G63. Our purpose is therefore narrow. We place on record an explicit public certificate for G63 with cut value 27,052, together with the information required for independent verification. We do not claim that 27,052 is the global optimum for G63.

2 Result

Table 1 summarizes the result. Relative to the best prior explicit public certificate we identified, reported by Khan and Shukla [2], the present assignment improves the explicit public certificate for G63 by 5.

Table 1: G63 result relative to the best prior explicit public certificate we identified.

Instance	n	Best prior explicit		
		public certificate	This work	Improvement
G63	7,000	27,047	27,052	5

This first version focuses on the certificate and its verification. Search details will be reported separately.

3 Solution encoding and cut recomputation

For compact presentation, we report the assignment as a plain hexadecimal string of length 1,750. Reading the string from left to right and expanding each hexadecimal digit into its standard 4-bit binary representation, most-significant-bit first (for example, hexadecimal A expands to 1010), yields the assignments of vertices 1 through 7,000 in the vertex numbering of G63. We use the convention $0 \mapsto -1$ and $1 \mapsto +1$, so

the two bit values encode the two sides of the cut. Because 7,000 is divisible by 4, no trailing padding bits are required.

To recompute the cut value, one scans the weighted edge list of G63 and sums the weight of each edge (u, v, w) whose endpoint assignments differ. Applied to the solution string reported here, this recomputation returns the cut value 27,052 exactly.

The full solution string is given in Appendix A.

A G63 solution string

The following plain hexadecimal string encodes the 7,000-bit assignment used in this note. Expanding the string to binary from left to right, most-significant-bit first (for example, hexadecimal A expands to 1010), yields the assignments of vertices 1 through 7,000. Applying the convention $0 \mapsto -1$ and $1 \mapsto +1$, and then evaluating the weighted Max-Cut objective on the standard G63 instance, reproduces the cut value 27,052.

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2382b78b8bdc8f57759286835ad3fb8bfb5e19d7fbc5ca9c389d87bc9da37b47fa0910d023ee118a393d9cd22c88be9adc8
9587ab126c7af153570434c9af77a2f728f57e8e7822a0381e1785d851a097f6a3ebb4f5e25f0b69730a2385aa2e337e4ef
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eb0c5ceeb57ecaab32bea6c941b8c6b729ff5b28b3ee10867718529cfafbf44a5435602ab1a5a7ed99e8426da2064b695e5
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31294efbedcc36243b6876ecb2f9f626f88148b41933a5ad17cf573438857e1a57190d7e040452f09c569995a6a09c60761
2846da31ebe7385cba7e1cee3b2cd5cf27ac4d32bd24bedcd7385a2ac193bf7aad5de17a7dcaeddaec73edc7bb80a634355
78a5c1b39ae4816d30269c487b9c52e89b08e790ecac908d0b6340975f5be08ea19be8c67ad4bade81d9cd5b4b3e8aba9295
b4545027a7078238ddbc6aad8fea0080a70e41cfa3f2d0b415b1177d37b3e153e1cde8573a5e1d30f33509cdb625feac161
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37a385ab5928aaaa7d6c96b6eaff3bdde92746f898593a42ddf10e5805ea32e5ea35a30b00544d13560313aa8dab051db
a8433d510c613422625ff8569df2a4f5744453260e7e3e8daf95b154d5710caa8226a6fe1661b24604bbb85930dfa3f048f
841431b8a6f9025d7e8b5d489cbc74567a11d9b94e3e71fcf38a48f268bd49fc0df3a558541ede39f7aa9499a5650afebf7
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49655b693826ef97403f7513e93085e9328b2527ee0d0e6d2f78b6332515b41bbcd22822bb093904a5a707717032e2689
5361f4acdbfce0126d9ddaa9a1ebbf3c0639172a8ce33e5276c348933bb1cea82af8523a859c08cbacdeb567d586c98080
8f3c063da6bef3565041685133f79097590c16fdeff623eb94a3427bc2268200d25
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References

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